

Enhancing human empathy in conversations using transformer-based models

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Abstract

Recent Large Language Models have gained much attention due to their performance in many downstream Natural Language Processing tasks and applications. However, they still struggle to identify human emotions, especially in multi-turn conversations accurately. This research aims to evaluate attention-based models' effectiveness in accurately identifying emotions. This work used the DailyDialog dataset, categorized into seven emotion classes. The dataset was cleaned during pre-processing, stopwords and punctuations were removed, and then the class distribution was balanced using random oversampling. Thereafter, the performance of three models (DistilBERT-base-uncased, RoBERTa-base, and BERT-base-cased) was evaluated on this dataset. Our findings demonstrated that RoBERTa-base performed better than other models, surpassing

the baselines with 68.50% accuracy and 75.45% F1 score, thus showcasing the state-of-the-art performance of RoBERTa in understanding human emotions in conversations. We also showed that RoBERTa works well with improved contextual awareness, thereby advancing emotion classification in multi-turn dialogues.

Keywords: attention-based models, daily dialog dataset, emotion classification, multi-turn text dialogues, transformers.

Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have become more empathetic and capable of recognising emotions via detecting, interpreting, and responding to human emotions using context-aware learning, affective computing, and psychology (Sorin et al., 2024). Emotion recognition focuses on identifying and analyzing emotions from text, visual, or speech inputs to recognize human emotional states. Therefore, classifying these emotions in conversations is critical and enables machines to recognize, understand, and respond with greater empathy and sensitivity within dialogues. Traditional models relied on one-hot encoding for emotion labelling, but these are limited in their ability to recognize overlapping emotional states. This work aims to understand how well transformers and attention-based models can accurately identify emotions in multi-turn text dialogues. Therefore, this study will help identify patterns within AI-based emotional recognition systems, which can help align them with human-like interactions and increase their overall empathic levels.

Literature Review

Many research studies consider enhancing LLM performance in emotional recognition as it enables AI systems to better recognize human emotions. For example, context-aware learning, in-context learning, and instruction tuning have improved emotion recognition from speech transcriptions, utilizing emotion-specific prompts, Automatic Speech Recognition Error Correction, and reasoning (Li et al., 2024).

Additionally, the Emotional Chain-of-Thought method has been shown to enhance emotional generation capabilities, with the Emotional Generation Score assessing its reliability (Z. Li et al., 2024). Also, research on situational awareness allows models to apply training knowledge in unrelated test scenarios. Larger model sizes and data augmentation have improved performance (Berglund et al., 2023).

However, several gaps remain. Traditional models using one-hot encoding for emotion labelling face limitations in recognizing overlapping emotions. So, grayscale labels were introduced in models like RoBERTa (J. Lee, 2022). Moreover, recognizing subtle and mixed feelings in multi-turn dialogues remains a challenge (Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2020). Additionally, advancements combining speaker and position-aware graph networks to model intra- and inter-speaker contexts (Liang et al., 2022) have shown promise but have not fully addressed the complexities of emotion classification in multi-turn dialogues. This study aims to address emotion classification in multi-turn text dialogues.

Methodology

Dataset

The daily dialog dataset (Li et al., 2017) is an English-to-English multi-turn high-quality dataset composed of 7 emotion categories of English utterances, classified as: no emotion (class 0), anger (class 1), disgust (class 2), fear (class 3), happiness (class 4), sadness (class 5), surprise (class 6) and different acts, for example "inform", "question", "directive", and "commissive". The dataset is divided into three splits: train, validation, and test, with three(3) features, 'dialog', 'act', and 'emotion', in each split. Having observed some class imbalance in the dataset, we found the median value of the majority class. We appended that count to upsample minority classes (e.g., class 2, class 3) by random sampling of the emotions in the minority classes. We also observed that the distribution of the conversation length varies between 2 and 25 utterances, while most dialogues are 3-10 utterances long. The distribution of the different emotion classes is shown in Figure 1A, and the Speech act distribution is shown in Figure 1B.

Experiments

To avoid skewness, each utterance is cleaned against duplicate tokens, the English stop words and punctuations, and then the class distribution is balanced using random oversampling. It acts as a mitigation filter against the influence of no emotion (class 0) over other emotion classes.

Three (03) models: 'DistilBERT-base-uncased' ([Sanh et al., 2020](#)), 'RoBERTa-base' ([Liu et al., 2019](#)), 'BERT-base-cased' ([Devlin et al., 2019](#)).

Models with experimental behaviour:

We used three (03) pre-trained models, 'DistilBERT-base-uncased' ([Sanh et al., 2020](#)),

'RoBERTa-base' ([Liu et al., 2019](#)), 'BERT-base-cased' ([Devlin et al., 2019](#)), with hyperparameter configurations as shown in Table 1.

The training batch size was set to 64. We tried batch sizes 16, 32, 64 and 128 and observed that batch size 128 overfits the model, whereas batch size 64 or less provided comparatively better results. We set a non-zero seed for the random initialization of weights that makes the neural network deterministic, guaranteeing that the same training process will produce identical results when repeated. We applied cased and uncased versions of DistilBERT, RoBERTa-base, BERT-base models, respectively, using the following hyperparameter configurations:

Table 1: Hyperparameter configurations

Item	Value
Number of training epochs	30
Learning rate	2e-5
Training and evaluation batch size	64
Weight decay	0.001
Logging step	10
Evaluation strategy	epoch

This work judged model performance analysis using accuracy and F1-score metrics. Training and validation loss behaviours for each model are shown in plots. Training and validation loss

plots for DistilBERT-base-uncased, RoBERTa-base-uncased, BERT-base-uncased and BERT-base-cased are shown in Figures 1C, 1D, 1E, and 1F, respectively.

Emotion Distribution: Counter({0: 72143, 4: 11182, 6: 1600, 5: 969, 1: 827, 2: 303, 3: 146})

Figure 1A: Emotion classes distribution in the Daily-Dialogue dataset

Speech Act Distribution: Counter({1: 39873, 2: 24974, 3: 14242, 4: 8081})

Figure 1B: Different Speech act distribution in this dataset

Figure 1C: Loss distribution of **DistilBERT uncased** model

Figure 1D: Loss distribution of **RoBERTa-base uncased** model

Figure 1E: For BERT-base uncased model for 30 iterations

Figure 1F: Loss distribution for 30 iterations

Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows the results obtained for the 3 models, including their cased and uncased versions. The last 5 rows of Table 2 show some additional models used in the experiments to compare with the performance of the chosen models.

Table 2: Performance values for all the models.

Model (50 iterations)	Accuracy (%)	F1 Score (%)	BLUE Score (higher better)	#Tensors saved during Forward Propagation (FP)	#Tensors saved during recomputation of gradient & backpropagation through time (BPTT)
DistilBERT-base uncased	59.60	60.41	6.66	80	30
DistilBERT-base cased	53.70	63.61	9.78	114	30
RoBERTa-base cased	43.6	53.58	9.81	136	30
RoBERTa-base uncased	68.50	75.45	5.86	191	30
Meta-Llama/Llama-3.2-1B	59.60	60.41	6.66	–	–
BERT-base cased	43.1	54.12	7.85	–	–
BERT-base uncased	43.0	45.67	7.833	–	–
BERT-large cased	38.8	48.84	7.068	–	–
BERT- large uncased	32.22	40.14	5.86	–	–

Our findings show that RoBERTa-base uncased model performed far better than both DistilBERT variants, with an accuracy of 68.50% and an F1 score of 75.45%. DistilBERT-base uncased had an accuracy of 59.60% and an F1 score of 60.41%, while DistilBERT-base cased had an accuracy of 53.70% and an F1 score of 63.61%. These findings indicate the superior performance of RoBERTa-base in emotion classification tasks on the DailyDialog dataset.

As shown in Table 3, our models performed well compared to the existing baselines. The

RoBERTa-base uncased model, having an F1 score of 75.45%, surpassed the EmoOne-RoBERTa model, which achieved an F1 score of 61.67%. That was a considerable increase of approximately 13.78 percentage points. In addition, our DistilBERT-base cased model, with an F1 score of 63.61%, outperformed the CoMPM and Pretrained Hierarchical Transformer with F1 scores of 60.34% and 60.14%, respectively. These comparisons point to the strength of our approach in surpassing several state-of-the-art models and standing competitively in the emotion classification task.

Table 3: Performance comparison of various transformer models on the Daily Dialog dataset

Model	F1 Score %
RoBERTa-base uncased (this work)	75.45
EmoOne-RoBERTa (B. Lee & Choi, 2021)	61.67
CoMPM (J. Lee & Lee, 2021)	60.34
Pretrained Hierarchical Transformer (Chapuis et al., 2020)	60.14
EmotionIC (Liu et al., 2023)	60.13
TODKAT+HCL (Yang et al., 2022)	59.76

Conclusion

In this work, we used the BERT, DistilBERT and RoBERTa models to recognise and classify emotions in multi-turn dialogues using the DailyDialogue dataset. Our findings depict that the RoBERTa-based Uncased model performs better than DistilBERT variants and existing baselines, achieving 68.50% accuracy and a 75.45% F1 score, validating its superiority in emotion classification. A major limitation is the overfitting observed in the models, which could not be fixed given the computational demands. In the future, we aim to apply datasets like IEMOCAP and MELP with a hierarchical transformer, multimodal approaches, and ethical concerns in empathetic AI. Further research will focus on enhancing model interpretability, addressing cross-cultural emotional contexts with applications in legal and high-stakes decision-making domains.

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References

- Chapuis, E., Colombo, P., Manica, M., Labeau, M., & Clavel, C. (2020). Hierarchical pre-training for sequence labelling in spoken dialog. *arXiv Preprint arXiv:2009.11152*.
- Devlin, J., Chang, M.-W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019). *BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding*.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1810.04805>
- Lee, B., & Choi, Y. S. (2021). Graph Based Network with Contextualized Representations of

- Turns in Dialogue. In M.-F. Moens, X. Huang, L. Specia, & S. W. Yih (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing* (pp. 443–455). Association for Computational Linguistics.
<https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.emnlp-main.36>
- Lee, J. (2022). *The Emotion is Not One-hot Encoding: Learning with Grayscale Label for Emotion Recognition in Conversation*.
- Lee, J., & Lee, W. (2021). CoMPM: Context modeling with speaker’s pre-trained memory tracking for emotion recognition in conversation. *arXiv Preprint arXiv:2108.11626*.
- Li, Y., Gong, Y., Yang, C.-H. H., Bell, P., & Lai, C. (2024). *Revise, Reason, and Recognize: LLM-Based Emotion Recognition via Emotion-Specific Prompts and ASR Error Correction*. <https://arxiv.org/html/2409.15551v1>
- Li, Y., Su, H., Shen, X., Li, W., Cao, Z., & Niu, S. (2017). *DailyDialog: A Manually Labelled Multi-turn Dialogue Dataset*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1710.03957>
- Liang, C., Xu, J., Lin, Y., Yang, C., & Wang, Y. (2022). S+PAGE: A Speaker and Position-Aware Graph Neural Network Model for Emotion Recognition in Conversation. In Y. He, H. Ji, S. Li, Y. Liu, & C.-H. Chang (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2nd Conference of the Asia-Pacific Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics and the 12th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (Volume 1: Long Papers)* (pp. 148–157). Association for Computational Linguistics.
<https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.aacl-main.12>
- Liu, Y., Li, J., Wang, X., & Zeng, Z. (2023). *EmotionIC: emotional inertia and contagion-driven dependency modeling for emotion recognition in conversation*.
- Liu, Y., Ott, M., Goyal, N., Du, J., Joshi, M., Chen, D., Levy, O., Lewis, M., Zettlemoyer, L., &

- Stoyanov, V. (2019). *RoBERTa: A Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach*.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1907.11692>
- Sanh, V., Debut, L., Chaumond, J., & Wolf, T. (2020). *DistilBERT, a Distilled version of BERT: smaller, faster, cheaper and lighter*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.01108>
- Wang, Y., Zhang, J., Ma, J., Wang, S., & Xiao, J. (2020). Contextualized Emotion Recognition in Conversation as Sequence Tagging. In O. Pietquin, S. Muresan, V. Chen, C. Kennington, D. Vandyke, N. Dethlefs, K. Inoue, E. Ekstedt, & S. Ultes (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 21th Annual Meeting of the Special Interest Group on Discourse and Dialogue* (pp. 186–195). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.sigdial-1.23>
- Yang, L., Shen, Y., Mao, Y., & Cai, L. (2022). Hybrid curriculum learning for emotion recognition in conversation. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 36(10), 11595–11603.